

INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES AND METHODS IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING

Ganiyeva Mubinaxon Farhod qizi¹, Kurbanova Muhabbat Mamajanovna²

¹student of TNI-4r-25, TSTrU

²Scientific supervisor, Associate Professor of the Department of Foreign Languages, TSTrU.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20307766>

Abstract. *This article analyzes the tools of nonverbal communication in the process of interaction and their importance in enhancing the efficiency of the communicative process between teachers and students. It highlights how nonverbal communication contributes to increasing students' engagement during lessons, fully capturing their attention during the educational process, and improving their comprehension of educational materials through examples. This study considers nonverbal communication as an innovative pedagogical method that enhances the effectiveness of foreign language teaching in modern educational environments.*

Keywords: *nonverbal communication, innovative teaching methods, body language, foreign language teaching, pedagogical efficiency.*

Abstract. *В данной статье анализируются средства невербальной коммуникации в процессе взаимодействия и их значение в повышении эффективности коммуникативного процесса между учителем и учеником. В статье освещается вклад невербальной коммуникации в повышение активности, учащегося на уроках, полное вовлечение их внимания в учебный процесс и улучшение усвоения учебного материала с помощью примеров. Данное исследование рассматривает невербальную коммуникацию как инновационный педагогический метод, повышающий эффективность обучения иностранным языкам в современных образовательных условиях.*

Ключевые слова: *невербальная коммуникация, инновационные методы обучения, язык тела, обучение иностранным языкам, педагогическая эффективность*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada muloqot jarayonida nonverbal muloqot vositalari va ularning o'qituvchi va o'quvchi o'rtasidagi kommunikativjarayonning samaradorligini oshirishdagi ahamiyati tahlil qilinadi. Maqolada nonverbal muloqotning o'quvchilarning darsdagi faolligini oshirish, ularning diqqatini dars jarayoniga to'liq jalb qilish hamda o'quv materiallarini yaxshi o'zlashtirishiga qo'shadigan hissasini misollaryordamida yoritib beriladi. Ushbu tadqiqot nonverbal muloqotni zamonaviy ta'lim muhitida chet tillarini o'qitish samaradorligini oshiruvchi innovatsion pedagogik usul sifatida ko'rib chiqadi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *nonverbal muloqot, innovatsion o'qitish usullari, tana tili, chet tillarini o'qitish, pedagogik samaradorlik*

There are several factors that necessitate the use of nonverbal communication tools in communicative acts among individuals. Nonverbal communication can be considered an innovative and effective pedagogical method in modern foreign language teaching. The first is the limitation of words in expressing certain directions, forms, or personalities. Secondly, the impact of nonverbal communication is relatively broader; while verbal communication is associated with visually observable elements; nonverbal communication is directly related to the

internal expressions of the speaker. For instance, a speaker might use positive verbal expressions about a subject while their nonverbal actions convey the message sarcastically. Thirdly, nonverbal messages are highly natural and occur precisely during the speech process. Unlike verbal communication, managing nonverbal communication is a complex process.

The study of nonverbal communication is a vast field, prompting numerous scholars to conduct scientific research on the subject. Specifically, linguist S. Mo'minov emphasized that as men and women differ in roles and social rights, their communicative behaviors also differ inherently. He provided detailed information on the nonverbal tools used in the communicative behaviors of men and women.

Nonverbal communication is not only an integral part of daily interactions but also a crucial component of the educational process between teachers and students. Research indicates that nonverbal signals such as gestures, body language, facial expressions, voice, and physical positioning significantly enhance the effectiveness of communication between teachers and students. These components ensure the efficient exchange of knowledge, skills, and emotions during the educational process.

Teachers' nonverbal behaviors strengthen the emotional bond with students and increase their interest in lessons. In the communicative act, the teacher performs a dominant role, meaning the initiation, continuation, and conclusions of communication are the teacher's responsibilities. Teachers actively use nonverbal tools in the classroom, often without realizing it. Albert Mehrabian's research indicates that in communication, 7% of the speaker's speech is conveyed through verbal tools, 38% through voice, and 55% through nonverbal tools. Based on this information, considering the high usage of nonverbal tools in communication, it is essential to pay more attention to their functions aimed at improving educational quality. Thus, nonverbal tools are used during lessons for the following purposes:

- Reducing the time teachers spend on verbal communication.
- Capturing students' attention to the lesson
- Increasing mutual trust
- Ensuring classroom management
- Preventing misunderstandings

Enhancing lesson efficiency Researchers such as Tai, Negi, and Malathi, who have conducted various studies in this field, have also highlighted the importance of eye contact in information exchange. According to the researchers, proficient use of eye contact by teachers facilitates the teaching process and significantly impacts the effectiveness of lessons. We also believe that eye contact is particularly important in the classroom environment. For example, if students do not understand the topic, this is clearly reflected in their eyes, and the teacher can easily sense it through internal intuition. As a result, the topic is explained again in a simpler way or enriched with examples. Conversely, when learners understand the topic well, the interest reflected in their eyes signals the teacher to provide even more new and interesting information. Additionally, maintaining eye contact during the lesson increases students' trust in the teacher and the information being provided.

In modern English assessment systems, maintaining eye contact during conversations is considered an important factor for achieving high results. Therefore, students prepare specially for this process.

Unlike English culture, in ancient Uzbek traditions, maintaining eye contact with the teacher was considered a negative behavior, indicating disrespect towards the teacher. Students

were expected to stand humbly with their eyes downcast in front of the teacher. This is illustrated in the following excerpt from Sadriddin Ayni's “Old School” story:

-Sadriddin! degan tovush eshitildi. Qayrilib qaradim. Meni domla chaqirar edi. Yo'limdan qaytib dom laning r o 'parisida, unga k o 'zimni tikkan liolda to 'xtadim.

Qo'lingni qovushtir dedi domla, bir daraja rizosizlik bilan. (Sadriddin! - a voice was heard. I turned back. The teacher was calling me. I returned and stood in front of him, staring into his eyes. - "Fold your hands," said the teacher with a hint of displeasure.)

This excerpt shows that the act of “staring into his eyes,” or violating cultural norms, caused the teacher's "displeasure."

The president of a major consulting company on the East Coast emphasizes the importance of informal gestures as follows: He raises his right hand and makes a circle with his index finger and thumb, then asks new employees to do the same. When everyone makes the thumb circle, the president asks them to touch the circle to their chin, but he himself touches the circle to his cheek. What is the result? About 80% of the group members do not do what the president says (touching the cheek) but rather what they see (touching the chin). This example shows that many people observe the person in the leadership role and unconsciously imitate their actions. Since the teacher also performs a leadership role during the lesson, any action they take is likely to be observed and imitated by the learners. Therefore, the teacher's knowledge of using nonverbal tools is significant.

In conclusion, the importance of nonverbal communication in the educational process is distinctive. By effectively using nonverbal signals, teachers can increase students' participation in lessons, capture their attention, and help them better understand educational materials. Therefore, it is necessary to further study and research the role and importance of nonverbal communication in the educational process.

References

1. Mo'minov, S. (2021). *O'zbek muloqot xulqining ijtimoiy-lisoniy hususiyatlari*.
2. Mehrabian, A. (1971). *Silent Messages: Implicit Communication of Emotions and Attitudes*.
3. Achilov, O. R., & Todjidinova, U. U. Q. (2023). TARJIMONLIK VA TARJIMA MADANIYATI MUAMMOLARI. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 3(4), 131-135.
4. Negi, J. S. (2009). *The Role of Teachers' Non-Verbal Communication in ELT Classroom*. *Journal ofNELTA*.
5. Kurbanova, M. M., & Ataeva, G. B. (2020). *Problems facing efl teachers in mixed ability classes and strategies used to overcome them*. *ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science*, 1(81), 721-725.
6. Malathi, S. (2013). *The Impact of Nonverbal Communication in Teaching*. *International Journal of Education and Psychological Research*.
7. Maratovna, J. X. (2025). *MODERN INTERACTION IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING*. *TADQIQOTLAR*, 76(6), 24-26.
8. Ambady, N., & Rosenthal, R. (1993). *Half a Minute: Predicting Teacher Evaluations From Thin Slices of Nonverbal Behavior and Physical Attractiveness*. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*.